

Influence of human body geometry simplification on local heat transfer

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.1404523

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Introduction

As the prediction on human thermal response has become the focus of research, plenty of human heat transfer and thermal regulation models appeared in the last decades. Considering computational cost, irregular anatomic human body structure is simplified in these models into regular geometries, such as sphere, cylinder and block. Heat transfer coefficients (htc) at the body surface are important parameters in these models for heat exchange calculations. The size and shape of the surface are bound to have influence on htc. Inaccurate htc due to geometric simplification may result in predictive errors in human thermal response and compromise the model validation.

This study aims at determining the influence of geometric simplification on heat transfer by comparing local and global htc at various body regions. This will help to find the balance between accuracy of htc and the level of human body simplification in the model reflected in computational cost.

Method

Two kinds of simplified geometric models were built using COMSOL Multiphysics 5.3a (COMSOL, Inc., USA) (Figure. 1). The first one is **a)** cylinder man which comprises one cylinder, and the other one is a tin man which comprises 13 cylinders and a sphere. The body dimensions and division were in accordance to the passive system of Fiala model [1]. The two simplified models were placed in a chamber model (5.3×3.2×2.74m) with a quasi-piston flow. Heat exchange between body and chamber was simulated by coupling turbulent flow and thermal flow in COMSOL Multiphysics software. In addition, an experiment with Newton-Asia manikin was conducted to get heat flux at the manikin surface.

Figure 1. Geometric representation of cylinder man **a)** and tin man **b)**

Table 1. Description of the datasets used for comparison

Study	Simulation			Measurement				
	cylinder man (this study)	tin man (this study)	Yang, 2017 [2]	Newton-Asia (this study)	Newton-Eur, 2015 [3]	SAM, 2015 [3]	de Dear, 1997 [4]	Quintela, 2014 [5]
Body geometry	Cylinder	Cylinder and sphere	Scanned male	Anatomic male	Anatomic male	Anatomic male	Anatomic female	Anatomic female
$T_{Env}-T_{skin}$	11°C	11°C	12°C	14°C	12°C	12°C	12°C	11°C
Air velocity	0.2m/s	0.2 m/s	0.1 m/s	0.43 m/s	< 0.2 m/s	< 0.2 m/s	< 0.1 m/s	0.2 m/s

Table 1 shows data source for comparative study. The htc values, including total heat transfer coefficient (h_t), convective heat transfer coefficient (h_c) and radiative heat transfer coefficient (h_r), were calculated by dividing heat flux with temperature difference between skin and environment.

Results and discussion

Figure 2 shows h_{tc} from different studies as listed in Table 1. A similar distribution of h_{tc} over the whole body was observed between different studies. According to Figure 2 a), the simulated h_t of the whole body for the cylinder man ($8.25 \text{ Wm}^{-2}\text{C}^{-1}$) and tin man ($8.30 \text{ Wm}^{-2}\text{C}^{-1}$) were close to de Dear's measurement. At head, chest, arm and hand parts, the h_t values of tin man fell within the range of values in datasets. The total h_t at Newton-Asia surface was found to be the highest, which might be due to the high air velocity of 0.43m/s . Locally, the greatest discrepancy between measurements was observed at hand with the maximum difference of $7.1 \text{ Wm}^{-2}\text{C}^{-1}$ between Newton-Eur and that in de Dear's study.

Figure 2. Heat transfer coefficient at individual segment. a) h_t , b) h_c , c) h_r .

As Figure 2 b) depicts, the simulated h_c of the whole body for the cylinder man and tin man was respectively 0.3 and $0.5 \text{ Wm}^{-2}\text{C}^{-1}$ higher than the measurement by de Dear et al. Locally, the h_c at hand was up to 1.95 and $2.26 \text{ Wm}^{-2}\text{C}^{-1}$ higher than the measurement by de Dear et al. and the simulation by Yang et al. Slightly higher air velocity might have contributed to this discrepancy. In addition, in tin man model, the hand was simplified as a cylinder with small radius of 2.26cm and great length of 31cm to reflect the hand surface area, which differed greatly from the anatomic hand geometry, which might be the reason for the high discrepancy. The h_r values at tin man surface shown in Figure 2 c) were almost $1 \text{ Wm}^{-2}\text{C}^{-1}$ lower than measurements by de Dear et al. at limbs. In de Dear's study, the h_r values were achieved by comparing h_t between the nude and the aluminum foil covered manikin. Only one leg and arm was covered at a time in his study, which led to greater effective radiation area than in tin man model.

Conclusions

Body geometry has few influences on h_{tc} distribution over the whole body, as well as total and local h_t and h_r . However, air velocity influences the h_t a lot, which indicates that air flow conditions should be well controlled while calculating heat exchange. For heat transfer simulation between body and environment, cylinders are available for torso parts, while geometries with more details are recommended for extremity simulation.

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